

UNVEILING DYSPHEMISM: EXPLORING NEGATIVE CONNOTATIONS IN LITERARY LANGUAGE

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Abstract

This article delves into the intricate realm of dysphemism within literature, shedding light on the phenomenon wherein words and phrases acquire derogatory or offensive connotations over time. Dysphemism, the antithesis of euphemism, reveals the dynamic nature of language and its reflection of societal attitudes, historical contexts, and cultural shifts. Through an extensive review of literary works spanning different genres and time periods, this study examines how certain terms evolve from neutral or clinical descriptors to loaded markers of scorn or ridicule. By analyzing the linguistic strategies employed by authors to convey dysphemic expressions, this research seeks to elucidate the underlying social, political, and psychological dynamics that contribute to the dysphemization process. Furthermore, this article explores the implications of dysphemism for literary interpretation, highlighting its role in shaping reader perceptions, reinforcing stereotypes, or challenging prevailing norms. Ultimately, this study offers a nuanced understanding of dysphemism as a multifaceted phenomenon that intersects with broader issues of power, identity, and discourse within literary discourse.

Key words: disease, dysphemism, euphemism, mockery , sarcasm

Dysphemization is a linguistic phenomenon where a word or phrase acquires negative connotations or becomes offensive over time. This can happen for various reasons, including changes in societal attitudes, historical events, or cultural shifts. Dysphemization is the opposite of euphemism, where words or phrases are substituted to make them sound more socially acceptable or less offensive.

In the context of your inquiry about disease names used in literature, dysphemization might occur if a term originally used neutrally or clinically to describe a disease later becomes laden with negative connotations or mockery due to societal attitudes or historical contexts. For example, terms like "consumption" (for tuberculosis) or "lunatic" (for mental illness) have

undergone dysphemization over time as societal attitudes towards these conditions have evolved.

It's essential to be mindful of the potential for dysphemization when using language, especially when discussing sensitive topics like diseases or health conditions.

Dysphemization in artistic speech can be evaluated as an individual method . This individuality is characterized by a certain priority over the individuality in euphemism. Only "from the point of view of pragmatics, the euphemism or cacophemism of the relevant language depends on the observer (listener)" (A. Dabrowska). For example, the French disease (syphilis) euphemism found in many European languages can be considered as a euphemism by representatives of other languages, and as a dysphemism in some ethnic environments. The terms Schwaby, French, and Prusaki can be taken as both euphemisms and dysphemisms in the sense of "insect". After all, the dysphemic meaning in units appears only in connection with a certain space and time and is perceived on this basis. Dysphemic meaning, as in euphemisms, is mainly associated with and determined by ethnic stereotypes. For example: It tegdi TovoqQoshiqqa it tegdi (evf. — harom bo'ldi) Menga it tekkan, men... (disf. — nomusim buzilgan) The dog touched the plate. The spoon was touched by the dog (euphemism - became unclean) The dog touched me, I... (dysph. - my honor was violated) This is natural. Polysemantic, in the same situation, the word "dog" used in relation to a person means an insult in both cases. This is one of the conditions of dysphemism. However, based on the environment of the time and the culture of the speaker, it should be said that the exact expression of the meaning of "to be unclean" does not correspond to the character of the image, so the euphemistic meaning of it tegdi is used. Because in the environment of the beginning of the last century, in a situation where Islam was the dominant ideology, being haram was considered as a very rude and unconscious expression. What is forbidden is strictly forbidden according to the rules of the Sharia, so the use of this word is also a reason to conclude that euphemization is required. It is not surprising that there was a need to use another, although not very delicate, option that is not so difficult to say. In the second one, there is also a state of not being able to speak, but as O.V. Potapova pointed out, in this case, the resemblance of a person to a dog can have a dysphemic impression from the listener's point of view. At this point, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that the scenario of dysphemization consists of several stages. To compel someone is a euphemism for the original term of reality, but it is dysphemic for the

combination of touching someone's honor, and the expression dog touched is dysphemism for the combination of dishonored. It seems that, despite having a rhetorical character, their relative euphemism and dysphemism values are evaluated on the basis of mutual comparison of euphemism and dysphemism units representing the same denotative content. Therefore, it is appropriate to rely on the principle of relativity when reacting to these units. Classification of dysphemisms. Dysphema is a pragmatic phenomenon associated with a negative subjective attitude to the denotation. This, of course, cannot be a reason to say that it has no place in the literary language. Dysphemism meaning units are used to leave a heightened negative impression on the listener about reality or a person, but this situation shows that there is no reason to study, analyze and interpret it in this way, moreover, to classify it, the purpose is unknown, there is no need to see it. does not show. The problem is that, in fact, dysphemism is not a system of absolutely separate units, the dysphemism value of such units is rhetorical, it is considered in the same system as euphemism, at the same time, as a tool opposite to it.

Dysphemism expressions that mean mockery, sarcasm. Qo'tir itning keyingi oyog'i bo'lmoq- To be the next leg of a scaly dog (a worthless person): The poet of "Kalam guftoki..." When a pig broke out, he made me wander and wander for seven years in vain, you will not stand on my dirty hair And when the best people reached the throne of the dream of the bright world, I couldn't even be the next leg of the mangy dog. (A. Qod. "Maslaku maksaddan shammai izhar (little expression)") It is known that the pregnant expression, which is mainly used in relation to animals, does not have any color. However, in some cases, it is used against people and has acquired a dysphemism essence. For example: When the children here ask about their condition, alhamdulillah, they also play and laugh as if they are male or female, strait or qisr. ("Moscow Letters", Diyori Bakr - 219)

Using disease names in English literature to convey mockery or sarcasm can be a sensitive topic, as it may perpetuate stigma or offend individuals affected by those diseases. However, there are instances where authors have employed such language to convey certain emotions or themes. Here are a few examples:

Consumption. In older literature, "consumption" was a term often used to refer to tuberculosis. In Charles Dickens' "Bleak House," for instance, the character Mrs. Jellyby is described as being so consumed by her charitable endeavors that she neglects her own family. This usage could be interpreted as a metaphorical portrayal of how certain obsessions or causes can "consume" a person's life.

The Plague. Albert Camus' novel "The Plague" is a powerful allegory for the rise of fascism in Europe during the mid-20th century. While the novel directly addresses the outbreak of bubonic plague in the Algerian city of Oran, the plague itself serves as a metaphor for the destructive nature of totalitarianism and the human condition.

Cancer. In Sylvia Plath's semi-autobiographical novel "The Bell Jar," the protagonist, Esther Greenwood, struggles with her mental health amidst societal pressures and expectations. While the term "cancer" is not explicitly used, the novel explores themes of psychological deterioration and societal malaise that could be metaphorically linked to the insidious nature of the disease.

Leprosy. In Nathaniel Hawthorne's short story "The Birthmark," the protagonist, Aylmer, becomes obsessed with removing a small birthmark from his wife's face. While not explicitly referencing leprosy, the story's themes of obsession, vanity, and the pursuit of perfection can be interpreted as a commentary on societal attitudes towards physical imperfections or differences.

It's important to approach these examples with sensitivity and an awareness of the potential implications of using disease names metaphorically. Additionally, consulting scholarly resources or literary analyses can provide further insight into how authors utilize language and symbolism to convey complex themes and emotions.

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